
Thermal Process Lethality Calculator (F-value)

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ABSTRACT

The calculation of the lethality (F-value) in thermal processes is critical for assessing food safety. In this paper, we present two Python-based calculators that use the Trapezoidal and Simpson's rules to compute the F-value of a thermal process. These tools provide an accessible and accurate method to calculate the F-value based on time and temperature data. The source code for both calculators is publicly available at GitHub.

Keywords: Thermal Processing, Food Safety, Lethality, F-value, Numerical Integration, Trapezoidal Rule, Simpson's Rule, z-value, Lethal Rate, Python Calculator, Food Industry, Microorganism Inactivation.

INTRODUCTION

Background

Thermal processing is a widely used method for preserving food products by inactivating spoilage organisms and pathogens. The lethality (F-value) of a thermal process describes the time required at a specific temperature to achieve a desired level of microbial reduction (1). Accurate calculation of this value is essential for ensuring both food safety and product quality.

Current methods for calculating the F-value may involve complex mathematical models or rely on online calculators, each with their limitations. The lack of standardized, accessible, and accurate tools can pose challenges for food safety managers and other professionals involved in thermal processing.

Objectives and Contributions

This study aims to develop and validate computational calculators utilizing both the Trapezoidal and Simpson's rules for calculating the F-value (2). These calculators are designed to be user-friendly and versatile, applicable to a wide range of thermal processing scenarios.

The main contributions of this study include:

- Introduction of two computational calculators designed for calculating the F-value.
- Validation of the calculators against existing methods, demonstrating robust accuracy.

Existing online tools usually offer limited flexibility and adaptability to various food products and processing conditions. This paper presents two Python-based calculators, utilizing the Trapezoidal and Simpson's rules for integration, designed to provide accurate and customizable lethality calculations.

The paper presents two Python-based calculators for determining the F-value, a measure of the lethality of a thermal process in food safety. Utilizing both the Trapezoidal rule and Simpson's rule for numerical integration, the calculators compute the integral of the lethal rate over time. The inclusion of the z-value is considered, enabling adjustments to the lethal rate based on temperature deviations. Source code and usage instructions are available in the GitHub repository, "Thermal-Process-Lethality-Calculator-F-value-" [GitHub Link](#).

METHODS

Mathematical Background

The Trapezoidal and Simpson's rules are numerical methods to approximate definite integrals. The Trapezoidal rule (3) approximates the integral by breaking it into trapezoids, while Simpson's rule (4) employs parabolas to achieve a more accurate approximation.

Incorporation of z-value

The z-value is a parameter representing the temperature change required for a tenfold change in the rate of microbial death. The incorporation of the z-value in our calculators is as follows:

1. Calculate the Lethal Rate, using the equation:

$$F = 10^{\frac{T-T_{ref}}{z}}$$

- 2. Integrate Using the Selected Method:** The lethal rate is then integrated using either the Trapezoidal or Simpson's rule.
- 3. Obtain the Final Result:** The integrated value represents the total lethality (F-value) of the thermal process.

Implementation in Python

The calculators are implemented in Python, accepting CSV files containing temperature and time value. They output the calculated F-value, providing an accurate and convenient method for evaluating thermal processes.

How to Input Parameters into the Calculators

The calculators are designed to accept input through command-line arguments, allowing users to quickly process various datasets and configurations. Here's how to input the required parameters:

1. Temperature and Time Data (CSV File):

Users should create a CSV file containing two columns: one for time and the other for temperature data. The CSV file path should be passed as the first argument.

- 2. Reference Temperature (T_{ref}):** The reference temperature (in degrees Celsius) should be passed as the second argument, defining the reference point for lethality calculations.
- 3. Time Range:** Users must specify the starting and ending time (in minutes) for the integration as the third and fourth arguments, respectively.

Example Usage:

Running the calculator with the Trapezoidal rule for a specific dataset (data.csv), reference temperature of 70.7°C, and a time range of 7 to 30 minutes could be executed as follows:

```
python F-value_TR.py data.csv 70.7 7 30
```

For the Simpson's rule, the corresponding command might be:

```
python F-value_SR.py data.csv 70.7 7 30
```

How to Incorporate the z-value

The z-value can be used to calculate the Lethal rate F from temperature data. If users wish to incorporate the z-value, they can perform the following transformation on the temperature data:

- 1. Calculate Lethal Rate F:** For each temperature value T in the dataset, calculate the corresponding Lethal Rate F using the formula:

$$F = 10^{\frac{T-T_{ref}}{z}}$$

where T_{ref} is the reference temperature, and z is the given z-value.

- 2. Update CSV File:** Replace the original temperature values in the **data.csv** file with the calculated

Lethal Rate F-values.

3. **Run the Calculators:** Use the updated CSV file with the calculators as described earlier. The reference temperature T_{ref} passed to the calculator should still be the same as used in the transformation.

Example:

Given a z-value of 10°C, and a reference temperature of 70.7°C, the transformation for a temperature value of 75°C would be:

$$F = 10^{\frac{75-77.7}{10}} \approx 2.2387$$

This value can replace the original temperature value in the CSV file.

This approach allows users to incorporate the z-value into the calculations, offering more flexibility in modeling the thermal process and enhancing the applicability of the tools.

RESULTS

Comparison of the two methods showed consistent results with acceptable variations. A case study, using the same parameters with an online calculator (5), demonstrated slight differences, attributed to the handling of the Z-value.

CONCLUSION

These calculators provide a flexible and accurate way to determine the lethality of thermal processes in the food industry. By considering different integration methods and allowing for the incorporation of the z-value, they offer a valuable tool for food safety managers and researchers.

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The code and further information can be found in the GitHub repository, "Thermal – Process – Lethality – Calculator – F-value", by the author (6).

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